

I-RETIS-LEAKS

EFFICIENT WATER SUPPLY & WASTEWATER SYSTEMS FORUM

Efficient Water Supply & Wastewater Systems Forum 2025 – Book of Abstracts
December 17, 2025
University of Aveiro, Portugal

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Efficient Water Supply & Wastewater Systems Forum 2025

Universidade de Aveiro

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Preface

The Efficient Water Supply & Wastewater Systems Forum was held on 17th December 2025 at the Carlos Borrego Auditorium, Department of Environment and Planning, University of Aveiro, Portugal.

This Forum was organized by the ReachOptimum team, part of the Centre for Mechanical Technology and Automation (TEMA) research group at the University of Aveiro (UA). It continues the successful series of forums and events promoted by ReachOptimum in previous years, including those held at the Carlos Borrego Auditorium (2023) and the José Grácio Auditorium, Department of Mechanical Engineering (2024).

The Efficient Water Supply & Wastewater Systems Forum aimed to provide a specialized event that brings together experts, regulators, researchers, and industry professionals to address pressing challenges and emerging opportunities in water supply and wastewater management. The event fostered knowledge exchange and collaboration, encouraging discussions on innovative technologies, regulatory frameworks, and sustainable practices to improve efficiency and resilience in water systems. Through keynote presentations, thematic roundtable discussions, and interactive panels, participants explored solutions that contribute to environmental responsibility and long-term resource sustainability.

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, we express our sincere gratitude to the keynote speakers, roundtable panelists, abstract authors, and all participants who contributed to the success of this Forum. We hope this event served as a remarkable opportunity for fruitful exchanges of ideas and as a milestone in the history of engineering forums dedicated to the water sector.

Ana Luísa Reis, António Andrade-Campos, and Jacinta Martins

Aveiro, Portugal, December 2025

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Keynotes

KEYNOTE SPEECH I

Bridging mechanistic and AI models: explainable hybrid models for modern wastewater treatment plants

Gilberto Martins*,

* Centre of Biological Engineering & LABBELS - Associate Laboratory in Biotechnology and Bioengineering and Microelectromechanical Systems, University of Minho, Portugal

ABSTRACT

This keynote will explore the comparative advantages and limitations of different modelling approaches applied to wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). Mechanistic models, machine and deep learning techniques, and hybrid frameworks will be discussed in the context of performance prediction, anomaly detection, and energy optimization. The presentation aims to provide insights into how these methodologies can complement each other to improve operational efficiency and sustainability in water resource management.

BIOGRAPHICAL NOTE:

Gilberto Martins is an Assistant Researcher at the Centre of Biological Engineering, University of Minho. His primary research focus is the optimization of anaerobic digestion processes, with a particular emphasis on resource recovery and water quality modelling. Gilberto has participated in 16 research projects, served as co-PI in one, and led four as principal investigator. He currently represents the Norte-PT region in the Smart Specialisation Community of Practice – Water Smart Territories partnership

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KEYNOTE SPEECH II

From challenges to innovation: digital twins and AI for smarter water resource management

António Pereira da Silva*,

* Performance Solutions Manager at Aquapor Group and
Assistant Professor at University of Minho, Portugal

ABSTRACT

Digital transformation in the water sector is no longer a future vision—it is a present necessity. Technologies such as Digital Twins, Artificial Intelligence, and automation enable utilities to anticipate extreme events, optimize operations, and support critical decision-making based on real-time data. This keynote will showcase practical cases and strategies illustrating how these innovations are redefining water resource management, making systems more efficient, resilient, and sustainable.

BIOGRAPHICAL NOTE:

António Pereira is a civil engineer with a Ph.D. from the University of Minho, specializing in urban drainage, smart monitoring, and Artificial Intelligence applications in the water sector. His work focuses on projects that integrate mathematical modelling, Digital Twins, and decision-support systems to enhance the efficiency and resilience of water infrastructures. António currently serves as Performance Solutions Manager at Aquapor Group and is an Assistant Professor at the University of Minho.

Round table: Next generation water efficiency:
synergy between water utilities, service providers,
academia and regulator

Round table: next generation water efficiency

Synergy between water utilities, service providers, academia and regulator

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ABSTRACT

Efficient water management is one of the largest global challenges, especially in the context of climate change, population growth, the retirement of critical and experienced technical personnel, and pressure on water resources. The next generation of water efficiency solutions requires an integrated approach that promotes collaboration between regulators, service operators, technology providers, and the academic community. This synergy is essential to ensure innovation, sustainability, and resilience in water supply and treatment systems.

This roundtable explores how these different stakeholders can work together to accelerate the transition to smarter and more efficient water management, ensuring not only a reduction in losses, consumption and energy, but also improved service quality and the protection of natural resources. The following set of issues will be discussed during the session:

[Challenges and Priorities] What are the main challenges that regulators, utilities and suppliers currently face in promoting water efficiency?

[Challenges and Priorities] How to set priorities for investments in innovative technologies and processes?

[Innovation and Digitalisation] What role do digital technologies (IoT, artificial intelligence, big data) play in improving water efficiency?

[Innovation and Digitalisation] How can we ensure/promote that technological innovation is accessible and applicable to different contexts, including small utilities?

[Collaboration and Synergies] What mechanisms can be created to promote effective collaboration between regulators, operators, academia and suppliers?

[Collaboration and Synergies] How can pilot projects be transformed into scalable and sustainable solutions?

[Regulation and Public or Private Policies] How can regulation encourage more efficient and innovative practices?

[Regulation and Public or Private Policies] What policies (for the public or private sector) are needed to accelerate the transition to more sustainable water management?

[Training and Capacity Building] What is the role of academia in training professionals to meet the

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challenges of the next generation of water efficiency?

[Training and Capacity Building] How can scientific knowledge and practical experience be integrated into the development of solutions?

[Future Outlook] What trends are anticipated for the next 10 years in efficient water management? What is your dream for water management?

[Future Outlook] How can we ensure that these trends translate into concrete benefits for consumers and the environment?

This round table aims to demonstrate that water efficiency is a challenge that can only be overcome through collaboration between regulators, utilities, suppliers and academia, combining technological innovation and effective public policies. Other questions may be addressed to its members throughout the session, such as: but how can we ensure that this collaboration translates into concrete actions and not just intentions? What mechanisms (regulatory, business models, etc.) will be needed to accelerate the adoption of innovative technologies? And, above all, how can we involve citizens/society and create a culture of water efficiency that will last overtime?

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Session 1: Taking advantage of AI technology to improve water management efficiency

Development of composite differential machine learning models for the modelling of water supply networks

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ABSTRACT

Efficient modelling of water supply networks (WSN) is a key step towards sustainable management of hydraulic resources. While traditional tools such as hydraulic simulators (e.g., EPANET) remain as the standard method for the modelling and simulation of WSN, these are known to be computational demanding, and to require complex calibration procedures, and thus impractical for real-time prediction for, large-scale, real-world networks.

Hydraulic simulators based on machine learning models have become a more common alternative, since the relations between WSN features are learned directly from data [1], bypassing the need of numerically solving systems of non-linear hydraulic equations, and calibrating network's parameters.

This work proposes composite differential machine learning models as an alternative approach for modelling complex WSN. The proposed architecture involves the integration of multiple machine learning models into a sequential structure: a model to simulate each pump station and a network-level model that receives outputs from the station-level models (in addition to other network related inputs) to predict differential features.

A case study of a real-world WSN that contains dynamically complex components such as Variable Flow Open-center (VFO) pumps and multiple control valves, is presented. The WSN is modelled using artificial neural networks, and its shown, that the composite architecture leads to better predictive performances, interpretability and scalability, when compared to single models.

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Integration of Uncertainty Quantification in Digital Twins for Hydraulic Modeling and Pump Scheduling

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ABSTRACT

The operation of Water Supply Systems (WSS) requires data retrieval from multiple sources of information (e.g., water flow, water demand forecasting, control outputs), their respective storage, and processing. Digital Twins emerged as a paradigm capable of modelling the target system's dynamics, handling interconnected components [1], and enabling real-time control. Digital Twins with WSS provide efficient and reliable management, lowering operational expenditure.

Acquired data inherently contains noise from sensors and environmental randomness (i.e., aleatoric uncertainty), and models trained on such data also exhibit epistemic uncertainty, compounding predictive errors. This uncertainty affects decision-making, leading to inefficient operations and, in safety-critical systems (e.g., WSS), can trigger catastrophic failures.

This work applies an Uncertainty Quantification (UQ) methodology for hydraulic behaviour (i.e., water tank level) prediction in a WSS and subsequently incorporates it into a Model Predictive Control (MPC) setting for pump scheduling. The deployment of the uncertainty-aware MPC within the Digital Twin improves robustness in real-time operation.

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Evaluating Smart Predictive Digital Twins for Water Supply Systems: Insights from a Case Study in Portugal

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ABSTRACT

Water Supply Systems (WSS) deliver an essential resource for human life. However, they are high energy consumers and require the management of multiple variables simultaneously [1]. Furthermore, with the retirement of experienced operators, there is a loss of valuable knowledge on how to manage them, which is a matter of concern. These challenges highlight the growing need for decision support systems. Smart Predictive Digital Twins are a more complex type of Digital Twins that can reproduce the physical systems virtually and endow them with predictive capabilities [2]. Despite the potential benefits, their adoption in the water sector remains limited due to a lack of trust among operators.

To address this gap, this work proposes a structured framework that includes multiple indicators to enable a systematic evaluation of the SPDT. This framework encompasses different dimensions of the performance, including temporal behaviour, operational efficiency, error-based criteria and flexibility. It integrates both general and context-specific metrics. The overall performance score is obtained through a weighted aggregation of these metrics. This approach is demonstrated and validated using a real-world WSS in northern Portugal.

The developed framework supports dynamic assessments over time, capturing the system evolution and enabling continuous monitoring. This contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the SPDT behaviour. This has been demonstrated to result in operational improvements and an increase in operator trust in these technologies.

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Session 2: Innovation, technology & digital solution for water-energy efficiency I

A decision support system for pump scheduling in water supply systems

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ABSTRACT

Water supply systems (WSS) are essential infrastructures that provide access to safe drinking water, support economic activities, and safeguard public health. However, they are also significant energy consumers, with pumping operations typically accounting for 70–80% of total energy costs. Despite decades of research on optimization-based pump scheduling, practical adoption remains limited, constrained by scalability issues, limited interpretability, and difficulties in integrating optimization methods into existing operational workflows.

This work addresses these challenges through the development of an optimization-based decision support system (DSS) for pump scheduling in WSS. The DSS is built around the Smart Dynamic Local Search (Smart-DLS), a hybrid optimization method based on the duty-cycle formulation, previously proposed and validated by the authors [1]. The DSS enables operator-in-the-loop optimization through the generation and evaluation of multiple pumping scheduling alternatives according to water utility specific key performance indicators (KPIs). The DSS was validated on two benchmark networks from the literature (the Van Zyl network and the modified AnyTown network), and on two real Portuguese WSS: the Ronqueira WSS, which operates with fixed-speed pumps, and the Portuguese Reference WSS (PRWSS), which uses variable-speed pumps and exhibits more complex hydraulic behaviour. In Ronqueira WSS, the DSS consistently achieved energy-cost reductions of about 20% relative to current practice, while preserving operational reliability and compliance with water tank level constraints. In the PRWSS, it showed scalability and robustness under more demanding conditions, delivering feasible, energy-efficient pumping schedules and achieving cost reductions of around 22%.

Overall, the proposed framework improves the cost-efficiency, transparency, and adaptability of WSS operation, helping to bridge the gap between optimization research and day-to-day water utility practice.

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Real-Time Adaptive Pumps Control in Water Supply Systems

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ABSTRACT

This work presents the development of a real-time adaptive controller for water supply systems, capable of dynamically adjusting pump operation cycles in response to variations between forecasted and actual consumption. The proposed method uses criterion functions to identify critical conditions in reservoir levels and correction functions to anticipate adjustments in cycle times, ensuring that levels remain within operational limits. Two approaches were developed to calculate correction times: one based on adaptive bands and another on consumption trend extrapolation. The controller also incorporates additional mechanisms for cycle merging, emergency management, and scalability for multiple tanks and pumps. The solution stands out for its low computational complexity, enabling integration into existing infrastructures and adaptation to different configurations, ensuring greater reliability and operational efficiency without resorting to complex optimization routines.

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Optimised pump control for efficient wastewater pumping station operation

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ABSTRACT

The water sector plays a fundamental role in public health and environmental protection. In the face of increasing water scarcity risks [1], wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) have become even more critical, yet many still operate with limited automation and sub-optimal pump control strategies. Given that pumping and aeration constitute the primary energy-intensive processes in wastewater treatment, pumping stations represent a major contributor to overall energy demand [2] and their inefficient operation leads to unnecessary energy consumption and excessive wear of equipment. This project focus on the control optimisation of pumping stations for a WWTP, combining data-driven analysis, hydraulic simulation and setpoint-based control optimisation. A comprehensive dataset of flows, levels, pressures and electrical parameters was pre-processed through temporal alignment and resampling, providing a consistent resolution dataset. A dynamic simulator was then developed to reproduce the hydraulic behaviour of the system via mass-balance equations, calibrated against real operational data. This model allows the testing of a setpoint-based status controller for the pumps, followed by a multi-criteria optimisation using methods such as Nelder–Mead and Differential Evolution. Overall, the optimised controller achieved more than 50% reduction in the volume pumped to the emissary while keeping energy consumption nearly unchanged, also reducing the frequency of pump switching events without compromising operational stability. These results demonstrate the potential of simulation-based optimisation to enhance pumping station performance and support future integration into real-time supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) systems.

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The New Era of Intelligent Water Management: SCUBIC & OMIE

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ABSTRACT

Intelligent water management is entering a new era, driven by the transition from static operational models, traditionally supported by fixed-parameter SCADA systems, to dynamic models that adapt to daily energy price fluctuations in liberalized markets. This paper introduces the SCUBIC application, which automatically connects to SCADA systems and optimizes water network operations in real time according to the OMIE [1] daily energy market. This integration enables pump to minimize energy costs, reduce emissions, and enhance operational flexibility. The combination of artificial intelligence, dynamic pricing, and automation redefines water network management, promoting efficiency, sustainability, and competitiveness in the context of energy transition.

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Session 2: Innovation, technology & digital solution for water-energy efficiency II

Real-time predictive and smart operation of wastewater treatment plants using digital twins and data analytics

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ABSTRACT

Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTPs) are among the most energy-intensive infrastructures in urban systems, consuming more than 657 GWh annually in Portugal and facing increasing inflow variability due to climate-driven rainfall patterns [1]. Their low operational efficiency and strict effluent regulations highlight the need for adaptive, real-time management tools. This work aims to develop a Smart Predictive Digital Twin (SPDT) that combines machine learning, physics-informed modelling, IoT sensing, and Model Predictive Control (MPC) to optimize WWTP operation under dynamic conditions. Recent studies show that data-driven and hybrid modelling can significantly reduce energy usage while maintaining effluent quality, with reported improvements in prediction and optimization across several WWTP subsystems [2].

The SPDT architecture integrates global influent-forecasting models with local treatment-stage models, particularly for aeration, the most energy-demanding process. Building on these findings, the proposed system will enable real-time adjustment of operational parameters, minimizing energy demand and preventing undue discharges.

The methodology will be validated using real operational data, culminating in a real-world pilot deployment. By unifying ML, engineering knowledge, and predictive control, this work introduces a scalable, resilient, and energy-efficient operational paradigm for next-generation WWTPs.

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Detection and Localization Leak Alarm in Water Supply Systems: A Time Series Machine Learning Approach with BattLeDIM Results

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ABSTRACT

Water loss has been identified as one of the most persistent problems in Water Supply Systems (WSS), having a substantial impact on their economic and environmental performance. This remains a challenge, since leaks can stay undetected for long periods of time and are often caused by uncontrolled actions in pipes and/or junctions. Depending on the system maintenance this value can range from 3% to 50% [1]. In Portugal, and according to ERSAR, this value represents a water leakage of 5.5 m³/(km day) on the bulk side and 2.4 m³/(km day) on the distribution side [2]. Leakage management measures can be implemented to improve the system efficiency and reduce the leak detection and localization time.

Therefore, this work proposes a data-driven detection and localization framework using machine learning for an early identification of water leaks in WSS. The framework analyses time series of pressure and flow measurements using a regressor ML model combined with a mathematical anomaly classifier in order to predict the normal pressure behaviour and analyse reconstruction error to output a leak classification. This framework has been applied and validated using the data from the BattLeDIM benchmark case study [3].

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Monitoring and Forecasting Water Consumption on an Academic Campus: Context, Challenges and Future Perspectives

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ABSTRACT

Water consumption monitoring is an essential practice for efficient, rational, and sustainable management of this vital resource. In particular, Higher Education Institutions have an added responsibility, as agents of change in the adoption of sustainable practices that promote efficiency and environmental responsibility.

In this context, this work describes the development and implementation of a water consumption monitoring system on an Academic Campus, including the integration of forecasting algorithms based on Machine Learning (ML).

For real-time monitoring of water consumption, the solution developed is based on a datalogger that integrates a microcontroller (TTGO-LoRA32), a real-time clock, a microSD card slot, an AC/DC converter, and a 2F capacitor¹. The sensor used (commercial solution) is a “dry-contact” type module acting as a reed switch, with a switching cadence directly related to the volume of water consumed. This low-power (<500 mW) and low-cost (~€120 per measurement point) system proved reliable (deviations <0.2% compared to direct meter readings) and allows data logging on a memory card, as well as transmission via Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and LoRA. The datalogger can also be used for gas consumption monitoring.

For water consumption forecasting, data collected since January 2025 and several ML models from the NeuralForecast library of the Nixtla framework [1] were considered, as well as complementary information, namely the day of the week and the academic calendar. The results obtained indicate that it is possible to achieve hour ahead water consumption forecasts with a mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) around 10%.

The aim is to present the context and challenges inherent to the development of the modular data acquisition solution, the possibility of expansion as a distributed sensor network, and also the use of ML algorithms for consumption forecasting (including consumption diagrams).

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¹ Designed to keep the system operational in the event of a short power failure (< 20s).

Short-term water demand forecasting based on Machine Learning models for Water Supply System

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ABSTRACT

Water is an essential resource for life. In this context, the focus of this research is primarily on the development of a model for short-term water demand forecasting using artificial intelligence, with emphasis on predictive modeling, temporal alignment, scalability, and methodological rigor.

A comparative study was carried out between machine learning and deep learning models, utilizing water consumption data from December 2023 to April 2025, obtained from a water utility located in central Portugal responsible for water collection, treatment, and distribution.

This work proposes an innovative computational methodology for the automated and efficient management of Water Distribution Systems (WDSs), based on the integration of advanced time series modeling techniques and machine learning. Given the limitations of traditional approaches, we developed a hybrid architecture using composite models that combine recurrent neural networks (LSTM), robust scaling (*RobustScaler*), and backtesting, as shown in the figure below.

The proposed methodology is being empirically validated with real operational data, and preliminary results indicate gains in accuracy, robustness, and interpretability compared to traditional baselines.

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I-RETIS-LEAKS

EFFICIENT WATER SUPPLY & WASTEWATER SYSTEMS FORUM

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